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Use of Role-Play and its Effect on Grade 10 Students' Speaking Skill

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Abstract Role-play has been publicized as the most encouraging activity that can engross students not only into academic language and literacy skills but also their interest. A growing number of manifestations and testimonies pointed out that role-play supports the development of critical skills, students must have to meet on the demands of the 21st century. On the other hand, there is minimal evidence that not all may be able to like or participate especially those who are still hidden on their shells. In a nutshell, the target of this present study was to find out what's the effect of role-play and its improvement to the Grade 10 students' speaking skills. In addition, the current search was aiming to investigate the students' perceptions and attitude towards role play. Two groups were involved in the study, the experimental and the comparison. The study was carried out in the Grade 10 English class at the Bantayan National High School. There were 24 Grade 10 students who were selected as a convenient sample. Their age ranged from 15-16. They were all non-native speakers of English living in Bantayan. The experiment was conducted to investigate the effectiveness of the treatment, which was done through quasi-experimental research. The instruments used for collecting the data were pre-test and post-test questionnaire, semi structured face to face interview and teacher's field notes. The pre-test and post-test results showed that there was a significant increase in both experimental and control groups. This tells us that role play aided students to improve their speaking. As a conclusion, both methods used in this study were equally and largely effective. The questionnaire results also revealed that the students' attitude towards role play was seemingly positive. The qualitative data gained from interview also revealed positive effects of their attitude. The other qualitative data is from teacher's field notes that gave an insight about the treatment in the experimental group and the main procedure of the class.

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